

RELIGIOUS BELIEFS AS A FACTOR OF PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL HEALTH

Shoira XUDOYQULOVA

Teacher of the Department of Psychology of Termiz State University

E-mail: soirahudojkulova34@gmail.com

Phone number: (88) 807 31 07

Mekhriniso SAYDALIYEVA

Teacher of the Department of Psychology of Termiz State University

E-mail: saydaliyevamekhriniso@gmail.com

Phone number: (99) 542 91 43

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021740>

Abstract.

in this article, the importance of religious belief not only as a psychological phenomenon, but also its importance in the mental and physiological health of a person is explained through theory and research.

Keywords: Religious belief, religious person, social environment, family, religious impression, behavioral motives, social-psychological situation, imitation.

Today, it is known that religious belief is of great importance in the development of a person's mental health, cognitive processes and volitional qualities, and it is proven in many psychological studies. Psychological states such as catharsis, meditation, repentance are becoming an integral part of religious practices. For this reason, the question of using religion for psychotherapeutic purposes is on the agenda in Western and Eastern families. American psychologist A. Boyzen believes that religion has the power to positively influence people to get out of crisis situations in their lives. Professor Valery Slezin, the head of the St. Petersburg Institute of Neuropsychophysiology named after V.M. Bekhterev, during the examination of the psychological nature of religion that affects family relationships, comes to the following conclusion: in the process of religious education received from youth, religious belief and prayer do not regulate all cognitive processes in the human body, but also restores the damaged parts of the mind. In addition, a number of scientists from St. Petersburg conducted empirical research and tried to find the mechanism related to mental changes in the process of performing religious actions, and as a result, they also obtained certain results. They discovered the healing and psychotherapeutic properties of prayer, which are divine phenomena, and concluded that prayer is a powerful healing tool.

The most important guidelines for ensuring mental health are that a person must have moral, intellectual and social qualities for spiritual and social coordination of religious belief.

It is known that religious beliefs help people find meaning in their lives and influence their emotions, behavior and mental health. 178 students were randomly selected for the psychological experiment conducted at Islamic Azod University in Torbat-e Jaam. The purpose of the experiment was to determine the specificity of the relationship between basic religious beliefs and personality traits. Three religious beliefs about Human, Existence and God were chosen for the study. Also, factors such as five personality factors: neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were identified and the correlation between them was studied.

The results of the study show that the main religious beliefs have a negative correlation with neuroticism ($n = -0.29$), a positive correlation with extraversion ($e = 0.28$), a weak positive correlation with openness ($o = 0.14$), a positive correlation with agreeableness ($\alpha = 0.29$) and has a high positive correlation ($\sigma = 0.48$) with conscientiousness. From the above, it can be said that the personality trait called openness has the lowest correlation with major religious beliefs and the personality trait called conscientiousness has the highest correlation. A person's self-awareness, understanding of the meaning of his life, and beliefs about his relationship to the Creator are clearly inversely related in neurotics, that is, the higher the level of neuroticism in people, the lower their faith. A high positive correlation is observed between a person's self-awareness, understanding of the meaning of his life, and his beliefs about his relationship with the Creator and the personality trait of conscientiousness. This means that in a conscientious person, these beliefs are formed at a high level.

Thus, the results of this study confirm the religious cognitive-emotional theory that there is a relationship between religious beliefs and positive personality traits.

B.David who works at the US National Health Research Center. According to Larson and his team, when comparing religious and non-religious Americans, the results were remarkable. For example, religious people have 60% less heart disease than people with little or no religion, 100% lower suicide rates, and significantly lower rates of high blood pressure than smokers, compared to smokers by a 7:1 ratio.

A study published in the International Journal of Psychiatry in Medicine, an important scientific resource in the medical world, found that people who identify as agnostic are sicker more often and live shorter lives. According to the results of the research, non-religious people suffer from gastrointestinal diseases up to twice as often as religious people, and their death rate from respiratory diseases is 66% higher than religious people. Non-religious, secular psychologists refer to numbers like this as "Psychological Effects". This means that religious belief lifts people's spirits and this has a positive effect on their health. Perhaps this explanation is true, but more interesting conclusions emerge when this topic is examined in depth. Belief in God is stronger than any other psychological influence. An extensive study conducted by Dr. Herbert Benson of Harvard Medical School on the relationship between religious belief and mental health has produced some remarkable findings in this area. Despite being agnostic himself, Dr. Benson concluded that prayer and belief in God had more positive effects on human health than anything else. Benson also concludes that no belief can provide more peace of mind than belief in God.

In conclusion, in the words of the researcher Benson, the human body and soul are adjusted to believe in God. Modern medicine is now in the process of understanding this fact. As Patrick Glynn writes, "Scientific research in psychology over the next twenty-five years has shown that religious belief is one of the most consistent associations between mental health and happiness in general".

References:

1. Herben Benson and Mark Stark, Timeless Healing, (New York: Simon & Schuster: 1996), 203.
2. Patrick Glynn, God: The Evidence, The Reconciliation of Faith and Reason in a Postsecular World (California: Prima Publishing: 1997), 193

3. Glin, God: The Evidence, The Reconciliation of Faith and Reason in a Postsecular World, 60-61.
4. The Role of Parental Psychology in the Formation of a Particular Religious Beliefs in A Child. S. Xudoyqulova, M. Saydaliyeva - Eurasian Scientific Herald, 2023.
5. Psychodiagnosics of the relationship between agressiveness and religion in adolescents (In muslim and christian teenagers). M Saydaliyeva - Modern Science and Research, 2023
6. Manifestation of destructive religious behavior in personal characteristics. D Muhiddinova, M Saydaliyeva - Modern Science and Research, 2023
7. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3428642/> Iran J Psychiatry. 2012 Spring; 7(2): 82–86
8. Ismoilovna, A. Z. (2022). Prerequisites for identifying gifted children and shaping their abilities. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(6), 308-311.
9. Каракулович Ю. А., Исmoilовна А. З. (2021). ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭМОЦИЙ И ЭМОЦИЙ В МИРОВОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(10), 419-421.

